

CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT ASSESSMENT, HAZARD RISK OF FLASH FLOODS AND PREPAREDNESS IN DISTRICT DADU SINDH PAKISTAN

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Abstract

District Dadu is especially vulnerable to flash floods originating from the Kirthar mountain ranges. Hazard risk assessment and impact analysis to reduce the risk of flash flood damage in District Dadu's vulnerable areas, particularly Taluka Johi and some Khairpur Nathan Shah Union Councils (UCs) were carried out. Heavy rainfall can cause flash floods or hill torrents, which are characterized by abrupt water surges and serious risks to infrastructure and populations. This research emphasizes how these hazards may be considerably decreased with the appropriate combination of infrastructure, technology, and community involvement. These floods differ significantly from riverine floods in that they inundate areas in a matter of hours, giving very little time for preparedness. The catastrophic power of these floods is best illustrated by the Nai Gaj, a significant hill torrent. The floods of 2022 and 2025 demonstrated the enormous devastation that flash floods can inflict, causing homes to be submerged, inhabitants to be forced to relocate, and agricultural regions to be devastated. To improve flood readiness and resilience, the research outlines several crucial actions that must be taken, including remodeling and upgrading drainage networks and enhancing current irrigation and drainage systems to accommodate rising floodwater capacities. To encourage the natural flow of water, restore channels like Western Nara. Improve the RBOD/MNVD drainage systems' ability to handle floodwaters. Remove obstacles to enhance water flow in waterways. To absorb surplus water, restore and preserve trees in riverine areas and natural water paths, periodically replace and fix barriers that protect rivers and drainage systems, and Use satellite technologies to provide fast reporting and monitoring. Install weather stations with equipment in key places to provide precise forecasts. For further security, strengthen the left bank of the MNVD and FP bunds. Set up mechanisms to alert localities to approaching floods and keep an eye on Baluchistan runoff all during the monsoon season. The study promotes a multimodal approach to forecasting by identifying the intensity and path of precipitation using satellite photos and weather radar. Create rainfall-runoff models and track soil moisture content to forecast the probability of floods. For mapping land usage and topographic analysis, utilize GIS. Install river/stream gauges and Automated Weather Stations (AWS) for continuous monitoring. Organize public awareness initiatives and provide training to local observers. Use machine learning algorithms

and remote sensing technology. Encourage collaboration across agencies and incorporate data from several sources. To enhance predictions, run simulations and examine past data. Following an analysis of the effects, it was suggested that District Dadu should establish a strong FEWS since it offers several advantages, including early warnings that enable inhabitants to take the appropriate safety precautions and evacuate if needed. Enables local government bodies to gather resources and put flood prevention measures into action. Promote readiness in the community, strengthening resilience overall. Aids in the efficient resource allocation of government and humanitarian groups. Minimize financial losses by preserving houses, companies, and agricultural lands, and protects important habitats that are impacted by flooding. Above all, to increase confidence and promote collaboration between local authorities and the community in the case of flooding.

District Dadu's frequent and destructive flash floods make a comprehensive Flood Early Warning System (FEWS) necessary. The district can greatly lessen the effects of floods, save lives and property, and improve community resilience by putting the suggested strategies into practice. In order to establish a safer and more prepared environment for everyone, the study highlights the significance of a well-rounded strategy incorporating technical breakthroughs, infrastructure upgrades, and community participation.

Introduction

In the last few years, the Sindh province of Pakistan has been frequently hit by disasters. These disasters driven by climate change have been observed in the form of floods, heavy rain, drought, cyclones, sea level rise, coastal land erosion, and high tidal surges. These environmental hazards have adverse effects on the infrastructures, agriculture, livestock, fisheries, and income sources. District Dadu, located in Sindh, Pakistan, is particularly vulnerable to Hydro-Meteorological disasters. The mighty River Indus flows on the eastern side, while several hill torrents lead from the Kirthar Mountain situated on the western side. Additionally, numerous drains are linked to the RBOD project, and Lake Manchhar covers an area of 350 sq. km at the foot of the Kirthar range in the district. The water volume of these aquatic resources, when increased, leads to disasters that wash away everything in their path. Due to its geographic position about the Indus River and its effluents as well as the hill torrents, District Dadu is affected by floods quite often. Flood affects the lives of human beings, properties, farming, and

livelihood in the region. Familiarizing the spatial distribution of flood vulnerability is significant in the development of efficient disaster mitigation and preparedness plans. Location, elevation, physical features, irrigation network, hill torrents, wetlands, flood vulnerability in irrigated and rain-fed areas' geospatial maps were also prepared under this project. GIS-based mapping illustrating hazard risk vulnerability occurring in the areas was formulated using Geographic Information System (GIS) technology for preparing maps of hazard-prone and vulnerable areas in the study region. This mapping provided an important understanding of the risks, aiding in the strategic placement of early warning technologies for effective disaster preparedness and response. The hotspots and locations of the study area were identified and visited where flash floods hit. There are four talukas in Dadu district - Mehar, Khairpur Nathan Shah, Johi, and Dadu - where climatic impacts have seriously destroyed infrastructures, agriculture, livestock, and fisheries. Historical records showed that Talukas Johi and KN Shah were the most vulnerable. Surveys by the Revenue Department and local

government, along with FRDP, have revealed about 40 dehs in Johi Taluka as completely or partially submerged under flash flood water during the 2022 flash flood.

Significance of the study

This study aims to strengthen institutional capacity, streamline processes and practices, enhance coordination mechanisms through DRR units, integrate disaster losses and impact data across all disaster management governance units at national, provincial, and district levels, and boost ex-ante disaster response decision support systems. Furthermore, it will strengthen the implementation of PDMA/DDMA through the formulation of implementation frameworks/strategies.

Justification

District Dadu is prone to flash floods, and the absence of a functional EWS exacerbates the risks faced by its inhabitants. This study is based on data related to water flow from hill torrents, rivers, ephemeral streams, floods, and flash flood risks in the district. The Sindh Resilience Project has not analyzed the impact of flash flooding in the multi-hazard vulnerability risk assessments (MHVRAs) in the District Disaster Management Plans (DDMPs). To address this gap, comprehensive research on hazard risk and impact analysis is required. The need for an effective early warning system in District Dadu is clear. The insights gained from this research will help in the development of a comprehensive EWS, ultimately enhancing disaster preparedness and resilience in the region. By addressing the research objectives and leveraging stakeholder input, this study aims to contribute significantly to the safety and well-being of the inhabitants of District Dadu. Keeping in view the above facts, it is necessary to plan a sustainable mechanism of early warning system based on proactive measures instead of reactive measures at the time of disaster. A comprehensive EWS typically includes:

- Risk Knowledge: Understanding and mapping flood-prone areas.

- Monitoring and Predicting: Using technology to monitor weather patterns and predict floods.
- Dissemination and Communication: Ensuring timely and effective communication of warnings to those at risk.
- Response Capability: Building the capacity of communities and authorities to respond effectively to warnings.

Methodology

Despite the evident need for an effective early warning system (EWS) in District Dadu, no functional system is currently in place to warn inhabitants of impending flash floods. The Sindh Resilience Project has not analyzed the impact of flash flooding in the recently developed multi-hazard vulnerability risk assessments (MHVRAs) in the District Disaster Management Plans (DDMPs). As a result, there is a pressing need for comprehensive research on hazard risk and impact analysis concerning flash flooding in the district.

Key Informant Interviews:

Since we were focused on collecting real-time data, and geographic locations were scattered, researchers decided to apply the purposive sampling method, with the help of this method we were flexible to add new respondents/samples based on referrals from the participants following the snowball approach. Participants were selected using purposive sampling to include diverse groups from villages, hamlets, hilly areas dwellers, KIIs from the district admirations, experts, and practitioners. The Target sample size is 60 survey respondents, 4 FGDs, and 15 KIIs. A cross-sectional survey was conducted in Dadu District, 60 respondents belonging to targeted communities were purposively selected as a sample for the survey. The respondents were served with a close-end questionnaire, developed to address the research objective of the study. Four focus group discussions were held, at Khairpur Nathan shah and Johi Taluka. A discussion point instrument was developed based on the findings of the survey and key themes emerged in KIIs to further

explore the topic understudy. The primary data was collected through in-person visits and conducted surveys, Key informant interviews, and Focus group Discussions. Instrumental Data Collection and Assessments Survey (Structured questionnaire). Interviews with Key Informants (semi-structured questionnaire). Focus Group Discussions. Participant Categories for FGD and KIIs:

- Government Representatives
 - Academic Scholars
 - Lawyers
 - Community Representatives/Local Leadership
 - Media Representatives
- The secondary data was collected through the researchers from the relevant reports, articles, blogs, libraries, and all available / published material.
- Historical Flood Data
 - Relevant Reports, Plans, and Articles
 - Remote Sensing Images
 - Meteorological Reports
 - Meteorological Data
 - Local Community Surveys
 - Satellite Imagery
- Quantitative data is analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Qualitative data is analyzed through thematic analysis to identify common practices.
- GIS Mapping
 - Quantitative Analysis
 - Qualitative Analysis
 - Pressure and Release (PAR) Model
 - Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) Framework
 - Community-Based Early Warning System (CBEWS) Model
 - Sustainable Livelihoods Framework.

Results

Climate change impacts

The Dadu district is increasingly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, which it manifests in

several significant ways. The region is already prone to extreme temperatures, and climate change is expected to exacerbate this, leading to even hotter summers and more severe heatwaves. These higher temperatures can reduce agricultural productivity, stress water resources, and pose health risks to the local population.

Changes in precipitation patterns have another critical impact. While the region typically experiences low rainfall, climate change could lead to more erratic and intense rainfall events, resulting in flash floods that can devastate crops, erode soil, and damage infrastructure. Conversely, extended periods of drought could become more frequent, further straining the already limited water supplies and exacerbating water scarcity for agricultural and domestic use.

The district's agriculture, which relies heavily on the Indus River for irrigation, faces additional challenges due to reduced river flows and increased salinity, both of which are aggravated by climate change. These conditions can lead to soil degradation and reduced crop yields, threatening food security and the livelihoods of farmers. Moreover, the district's biodiversity is at high risk due to climate change-associated with droughts and floods. Changes in temperature and precipitation can alter habitats, putting native plant and animal species under stress and potentially leading to biodiversity loss.

Flood vulnerability

Dadu District is highly prone to flooding, particularly during the monsoon season when heavy rain swells the Indus River and its tributaries. The district faces pluvial and fluvial floods time and again. The district's low-lying areas in the irrigated region are susceptible to inundation, posing risks to lives, property, and crops. Historically, the Main Nara Valley Drain (MNVD) follows the natural depression of the district and connects Hamal Lake with Manchhar Lake (Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Map of the Main Nara Valley Drain (MNVD) in Dadu District

The elevation map illustrates the varying elevations across the district, providing a detailed view of the topography. The highest elevation is 2143 m above the mean sea level (MSL), while the lowest is about 33 m above MSL. Hence, the elevation of the district varies between 33 m to 2143 m above MSL. The area with the lowest elevation is along the MNVD. The map is color-coded to represent different elevation ranges:

Blue color areas (33 - 40 meters): These are the lowest elevation zones, indicating areas with natural depression. These regions are primarily located in the eastern part of the district, including towns like KN Shah, Dadu, and Johi.

Beige color areas (40 - 60 meters): Slightly higher than the blue areas, these regions are still relatively low in elevation. Key locations in this range include Mehar, Sita Rd, Faridabad, and Radhan.

Purple color areas (60 - 80 meters): These regions represent mid-range elevations and are found in the central parts of the district, extending towards the west.

Orange color areas (80 - 300 meters): These higher elevation zones are predominantly located in the western mountainous parts of the district, including Wahi Pandhi.

Red areas (300 - 2,143 meters): These are the highest elevation areas prominently seen in the far western region of the district, including the Gorakh Hill Station.

The map clearly delineates the elevation gradient from the low-lying eastern plains to the elevated western highlands. This topographic variation has significant implications for flood vulnerability, agriculture, water management, and infrastructure development in the district.

Fig. 2: Elevation map of the district Dadu, Sindh – Pakistan

Based on the elevation, the flood vulnerability map is prepared and is depicted in Fig. 3. The map illustrates the varying levels of flood risk across the district of Dadu in Sindh, Pakistan. The map is color-coded to indicate different flood risk zones. Blue areas represent regions at high risk of flooding. Yellow areas indicate regions with a medium risk of flooding. Green areas denote regions with a low risk of flooding. The topography of the region is depicted, with the

western part of the district, including Gorakh Hill, being more elevated and less prone to flooding, while the eastern parts are flatter and more susceptible to flooding. This visualization aids in understanding the geographic distribution of flood vulnerability in District Dadu, highlighting the need for targeted flood management and mitigation efforts in high and medium-risk areas.

Fig. 3: Elevation map of the district Dadu, Sindh – Pakistan

The district faces a high flood risk due to hill torrents from the Khairthar Mountains and runoff from generated at Nari, Mula and Kachhi basins in Balochistan. Approximately 25% of Balochistan's area drains into Sindh (Fig. 4). The runoff from the Nari, Mula, and Kachhi basins flows towards Sindh, entering the Kambar

Shahdaddock district via Chukhi. It then follows a natural depression strip (high flood risk zone), 4 to 8 km wide, along the MNVD route, traversing the entire district, and ultimately discharges into the Indus River through Manchhar Lake via the Aral and Danistar Canals (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Map of the area of Baluchistan draining into Sindh.

Different communities, civil society, academia, district bar associations, NGOs, and Government authorities were engaged to gather accurate ground knowledge through FGDs, KIIs, and workshops. The questionnaire consisted of semi-structured and structured questions; however, the respondents were asked at the end if they could add any other information or experience.

Interviews were conducted with sixty community members from Taluka Mehar, Khairpur Nathan Shah, Johi, and Dadu. Most respondents (82%) stated that to swiftly relocate to safe areas, they require an easy-to-use excess early warning system. Dadu district's rural inhabitants are severely impacted by the effects of climate change,

particularly flash floods caused by rainfall flowing from Kirhar Mountain Row, which is located on the western side. It is currently thought that global climate change is a fact that is eradicating. About 81% of rural community participants pointed out that flesh flood is the most common disaster among other calamities like river floods, heavy rains, cyclones heat waves, and droughts, etc. They said that they are losing jobs and face threats to their lives and livelihoods. Responding to questions related to government and NGO roles they said that there does not exist any streamlined mechanism to help and support vulnerable communities. Some NGO helped vulnerable communities at the time of the incident in connection by building and repairing

boats and houses, making available food items, drinking water facilities, and clothes, arranging medical camps, and providing training on alternative livelihood opportunities. Our survey revealed that awareness about flash floods is high among the residents of District Dadu. The devastating floods of 2010 and 2022 are still fresh in everyone's memory. Residents shared their harrowing experiences and highlighted the lack of pre-disaster measures.

Participants suggested several improvements to the EWS, including:

- **Enhanced Communication Channels:** Utilize telephone, Loudspeakers, wireless, mobile, electronic media, colored flags, sirens, colored beam lights from the mountains, and social media to disseminate early warnings.
- **Training and Awareness Programs:** Conduct regular training sessions to educate the community about early warning signs and actions to take. In addition, most of the respondents shared that mock drills and simulations can increase the efficiency of the community in facing such events.
- **Infrastructure Improvements:** Strengthen transportation systems and ensure availability of vehicles and boats for evacuation. Additionally, a few respondents shared that afforestation in mountains and on paths of drains can increase the lead time by one to two hours.

The Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with targeted communities aim to understand the needs and perspectives of people directly affected by disasters. This method ensures that the research considers the local context, community dynamics, and practical aspects of implementing Early Warning (EW) systems in disaster-prone areas. Key stakeholders, including village organizations and notable individuals from the targeted areas, were involved in various exercises and workshops to finalize the research study document and other materials. Community organizations, activists, journalists, and lawyers working in Dadu were proposed for this Hazard Risk and Impact Analysis Research Study to improve the Flash Flood Early Warning System (EWS) and preparedness in District Dadu. FGDs

and consultation meetings were arranged. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected accurately. Inclusive practices ensured that all community members were considered during the Hazard Risk and Impact Analysis Research Study for enhancing the Flash Flood Early Warning System (EWS) and preparedness in District Dadu. The focus group discussions and survey results highlight the urgent need for a comprehensive Early Warning System (EWS) in District Dadu. By enhancing communication channels, conducting training programs, and improving infrastructure, we can significantly reduce the impact of flash floods on vulnerable communities. Experts and community members stressed the need to enhance early warning systems to safeguard lives and properties. Participants highlighted the scientific approach needed to deal with natural calamities, which are currently lacking in our region. The most important task is to inform the community that they may be affected by the disaster through a warning system and to carry out evacuation if necessary. Additionally, there should be only one responsible agency or officer who is designated and authorized to issue the warning at the district level. This will help avoid miscommunication and ensure that people respond appropriately, as too many warnings from different sources can lead to confusion and non-responsiveness.

Discussion

An automated weather Radar system shall be installed locally around the border of Dadu district and Khuzdar, Baluchistan catchment area that must have the ability to track in real-time, the intensity and movement of precipitation. Satellite data and radar of PMD must be connected to validate the locally provided AWS information. Use satellite data to monitor weather patterns and precipitation over large areas [1], [2]. The models of rainfall create models to estimate the amount and velocity of water as well as to predict how rainwater will move through catchment regions [3]. Soil Moisture Monitoring should determine the amount of moisture in the soil to forecast the chance of

floods. Topographic Analysis through GIS study morphology of the area on the grounds of slopes and drainage networks. Mapping of Land-use and Vegetation Cover and its influence on water infiltration. Deploy automated Weather Stations (AWS) to collect real-time meteorological data. Install gauges to monitor water levels and flow rates in water ways. These devices should be installed around Gaj Diversion, FP Band, MNV drain and natural water ways to monitor run off velocity and volume and generate automated messages to DDMA and community in case if the flow observed high [4]. Establish networks to quickly disseminate warnings to communities and authorities. Implement mobile-based alerts to notify communities about imminent floods. These alerts must relate to rain gauge devices and disseminate automated messages in case of overflow. Local Observers may be designated members of the community to act as observers with responsibility for reporting weather conditions [5]. Public Awareness Campaigns may publicly inform the residents of signs of impending floods and necessary precautions to be taken. Remote Sensing technologies like LiDAR and UAVs to generate high-resolution maps; and create detailed flood models, predict flood extents, and plan mitigation measures. LiDAR-equipped UAVs (drones) can gather real-time data that could help make a quick decision before, during, and after the floods. Machine Learning and AI; Design algorithms to verify past data to make predictions of floods more accurate [6]. Interagency Cooperation; Improve collaboration between meteorological, hydrological, and disaster management authorities at all levels. Data Integration; Integrate Data from various sources to come up with more accurate forecasts. Based on the observations, Literature reviewed, and analysis of the satellite data, the following are certain recommendations. Up-gradation and Remodeling of Drainage Network in the Dadu District [7]. The current irrigation and drainage systems in the Dadu District need significant improvements to handle increased water flow and reduce waterlogging. This involves upgrading

the infrastructure to ensure that water is efficiently managed and drained from agricultural lands and populated areas. By remodeling the existing networks, the aim is to enhance their capacity to prevent floods, reduce the impact of heavy rains, and improve the overall agricultural productivity of the district [8]. Restoring the natural watercourses, such as the Wester Nara, is crucial to maintaining ecological balance and improving water management. This focuses on rehabilitating and reviving these natural waterways, which have historically managed the water flow in the region. The restoration would allow these systems to increase natural water discharge, thus reducing the risk of floods and ensuring that the water reaches areas that rely on it for agriculture and other needs. The Right Bank Outfall Drain (RBOD)/Main Nara Valley Drain (MNVD) is a key component of the region's drainage system. Enhancing its capacity is essential to managing floodwater more effectively. This involves enlarging or reinforcing the existing channels to carry larger volumes of water, especially during the monsoon season, which is critical for protecting agricultural lands and residential areas from inundation [9]. Zamindari bunds are private embankments constructed by landowners that often obstruct natural water flow in riverine areas. Their removal is necessary to restore the natural drainage patterns of rivers and streams. This measure will facilitate the unimpeded flow of water of the river, reduce the risk of local flooding, and improve the overall efficiency of the water management system in the affected areas. This initiative involves planting trees and restoring forests in riverine and waterway belts. The vegetation will act as a natural barrier, absorbing excess water and reducing soil erosion. It also contributes to the ecological balance, supports biodiversity, and provides natural flood protection by slowing down the flow of floodwater. Protective bunds along the Indus River, the Main Nara Valley (MNV), the RBOD, and other hill torrents need to be regularly upgraded and renovated. This ensures that they remain strong and capable of withstanding high

water pressures during flood events. Upgrading these bunds is crucial to preventing breaches that could lead to widespread flooding in the surrounding areas. The use of satellite technology for monitoring irrigation and drainage networks represents a significant advancement in water management. This technology will enable real-time monitoring of water levels, the health of drainage systems, and the identification of potential issues before they become critical. The data collected through satellites can be used to make informed decisions and implement timely interventions to prevent floods and water logging. Installing equipped weather stations at strategic locations, such as at the border of Baluchistan and the Dadu District, is essential for accurate weather prediction and monitoring. These stations will provide real-time data on rainfall, temperature, humidity, and other weather-related factors, allowing authorities to better anticipate and prepare for adverse weather conditions that could lead to floods or droughts. Strengthening the left bank of the MNVD and the FP bunds is necessary to enhance the region's flood defenses. Reinforcing these structures aims to provide greater protection against the erosive forces of floodwater and ensure the safety of the communities and agricultural lands located nearby. This infrastructure improvement is a key component of the broader flood management strategy. Implementing early warning systems is crucial for protecting communities from the dangers of floodwater. These systems will provide timely alerts about the approach of floodwaters from hill torrents and runoff discharges at Chukhi, giving people enough time to evacuate or take protective measures. The early warning systems will be a vital tool in reducing the loss of life and property during flood events. To establish a robust Flood Early Warning System in Dadu the following points should be considered. A dedicated Early Warning Center in Dadu: To ensure an effective district FEWS alerts in advance of approaching floods so that precautionary measures like evacuation can be adopted if needed, it is advance notification that saves lives and lessens injuries largely during

flood events. Risk-reduction: Effective FEWS enables local authorities, local emergency services, and even its military / police to pre-deploy available resources for the implementation of flood defense measures, including sandbagging and temporary flood barriers that may be very effective in protecting infrastructure and real property damages. Effective FEWS fosters a prepared culture in the community. Residents are better at planning and packing what would likely be required at the place of evacuation, and knowing evacuation routes, all of which enhance community resilience. Resource allocation efficiency: Timely alerts and Early warnings through dedicated FEWS centers from DDMA Dadu would allow the government agencies and humanitarian organizations enough planning time to ensure that response efforts, along with bringing aid into the most affected areas and organizing relief efforts will be more effective. By mitigating the damage from floods, FEWS can reduce associated economic losses from these disasters. Protecting agricultural lands, houses, and businesses from flood water translates to livelihoods being protected and supporting the local economy. Environmental Protection: Early warnings will also help in taking measures that ensure the protection of the natural habitats and biodiversity of a region. Anticipating floods, several measures can be taken to protect the crucial ecosystems that might get affected by the floodwaters. Community Trust and Cooperation: The act of setting up an effective FEWS will enhance community trust with local-level authorities. It may bring about in people the perception that the government cares and is interested in public safety and creates willingness to cooperate on evacuation orders and flood-safety measures. Given frequent and disastrous floods in District Dadu, the dire need is to implement an effective FEWS. This immediately cuts down on risk reduction, which will help towards long-term resilience and sustainable development by saving lives, property, and the environment. Continuous monitoring of runoff from Baluchistan, especially during the monsoon

season, is vital for managing water resources and predicting flood risks. By gauging runoff at critical points such as Chukhi, authorities can better understand the volume and speed of water flow entering the region. This data is essential for making informed decisions about water management, flood prevention, and emergency response planning.

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